

HYBRID COMPOSITES WITH A CROSSED-LAMELLAR MICROSTRUCTURE FOR STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY

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ABSTRACT

The damage tolerance of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs) can be enhanced by bio-inspired microstructural designs. Amongst molluscs, the crossed-lamellar microstructure is the toughest microstructure, despite consisting almost entirely of brittle ceramic. In this work, we explore original microstructures for CFRPs and metal/CFRP hybrid composites inspired by this crossed-lamellar microstructure. We demonstrate that composites with a crossed-lamellar microstructure exhibit extensive damage diffusion, while preserving their structural integrity up to record large curvatures. This makes them attractive for engineering applications where structural integrity is paramount, such as containment structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Despite being light, stiff and strong, CFRP is inherently brittle and CFRP parts show limited structural integrity, in that parts tend to fragment during damage growth or allow penetration during impacts. However, extensive research into new CFRP microstructures in recent years has demonstrated that the damage diffusion capabilities of CFRPs can be improved by careful microstructural design [1].

Natural composites, such as bone and molluscs, have proven an attractive source of inspiration for new CFRP microstructures, as they typically retain their structural integrity despite their weak and brittle constituents [2]. An example of this is the *Strombus Gigas* shell (Figure 1(a)) that has a crossed-lamellar microstructure as seen on the fracture surface of the shell in Figure 1(b) and schematically illustrated in Figure 1(c).

The *Strombus Gigas* shell has the toughest microstructure amongst molluscs, despite consisting 99.9 wt% of brittle ceramic [3, 4]. The toughness of the shell arises from the microstructure, which comprises three macroscopic layers (marked Outer, Middle and Inner in Figures 1(b) and (c)) with 0°/90°/0° orientation and, within each macroscopic layer, the lamellae have $\pm 45^\circ$ orientation with respect to the thickness of the shell. Upon bending, the shell dissipates energy through various strategies including parallel cracking on the tension side, and crack deflection, frictional sliding and lamella pull-out in the middle layer [3, 5].

In this work, our objective is to design, prototype and test first carbon fibre composites with crossed-lamellar microstructures. This entails investigating new microstructures for CFRPs and metal/CFRP hybrids. The metal/CFRP hybrid composites utilise both the crossed-lamellar microstructure and in-plane fibres. We demonstrate that these bio-inspired composite microstructures have attractive properties in terms of energy dissipation, and are ideally suited for applications where structural integrity is paramount.

2 CROSSED-LAMELLAR CFRP

2.1 Design and prototyping

We designed an original crossed-lamellar CFRP microstructure based on a detailed parametric study using a unit cell Finite Element (FE) model (see Figure 2). The microstructure was then prototyped using IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy prepreg with a 1:2:1 ratio of the macroscopic layer heights. New different pro-

Figure 1: (a) *Strombus gigas* shell [6]; (b) the crossed-lamellar microstructure visible on the fracture surface of the shell, after [7]; (c) a schematic drawing of the crossed-lamellar microstructure (not to scale), after [8].

totyping procedures were developed, investigated and compared, with the results presented here obtained using a bespoke bonding procedure.

The bespoke bonding procedure is based on first curing a thick laminate and subsequently cutting it into thin sections; these sections are then rotated and bonded using 3M ScotchWeld 9323 A/B toughened epoxy adhesive to construct the desired crossed-lamellar CFRP microstructure [8].

Figure 2: The crossed-lamellar CFRP was designed using a parametric unit cell FE model. The model is tessellated for visualisation purposes and shows diffuse damage at the ply interfaces in the inner layer and along the $\pm 45^\circ$ fibre orientation at a selected location in the middle layer, while the rest of the model is shown in bulk.

2.2 Mechanical testing

The crossed-lamellar CFRP microstructure was tested in a three-point bending (3PB) configuration in an SEM environment. Before damage occurred, the tests were paused at regular load intervals to take SEM images. At a later stage, when the damage was growing, the tests were paused at regular displacement intervals, or when other interesting features were observed.

2.2 Results and discussion

The test results of the mechanical tests of the crossed-lamellar CFRP microstructure are summarised in Figure 3, showing the specimen near the end of the test (Figure 3(a)) and the fracture surface of the specimen after the test (Figure 3(b)). The mechanical response of this novel microstructure exceeded our best expectations to such extent that the maximum displacement allowed by the tester was reached before the final failure of the specimen; the specimen was hence manually broken into two to investigate the fracture surface in Figure 3(b).

The failure mechanisms of the natural crossed-lamellar microstructure were successfully reproduced in the CFRP microstructure. The microstructure dissipated energy under stable conditions and exhibited extensive diffuse damage in the macroscopic middle layer, seen as deflected cracks along the length of the specimen in Figure 3(a). The extensive damage diffusion in the middle layer further manifests as large debonded areas and regular arrays of splits along the fibre direction on the fracture surface of the specimen (Figure 3(b)), while the damage in the inner layer was localised under the load pin (Figure 3(a)).

Figure 3: (a) The crossed-lamellar CFRP was tested in three-point bending, exhibiting stable damage diffusion in the middle layer and damage localisation in the inner layer; (b) the fracture surface of the specimen was characterised by large debonded areas and splits along the fibre direction.

3 CROSSED-LAMELLAR HYBRID COMPOSITES

3.1 Prototyping

In order to enhance damage diffusion in the microstructure, and to delay the failure of the inner layer, we conceived an original new type of hybrid microstructure, whereby we replaced the inner and outer CFRP layers of the crossed-lamellar microstructure by thin sheets of 0.4 mm thick 2024-T3 aluminium.

The microstructure was prototyped based on the same bonding procedure used previously, and the aluminium was etched in chromic acid before bonding it to the CFRP in order to improve the joint strength.

3.1 Mechanical testing

The new hybrid metal/crossed lamellar microstructure was tested in 3PB configuration in an SEM environment as with the previous microstructure. The tests were paused at regular intervals to capture SEM images and monitor damage growth in the specimens.

3.2 Results and discussion

The test results of the mechanical tests of the hybrid metal/crossed-lamellar composite are summarised in Figure 4. Figure 4(a) shows the specimen near the end of the test (the maximum displacement of the tester was reached before the final failure of the specimen). The microstructure dissipated energy in a stable manner, and the microstructure diffused damage effectively, demonstrated as an array of deflected cracks in the CFRP middle layer. The cracks did not grow very far into the middle layer and the microstructure preserved its structural integrity up to large deformations.

Figure 4(b) shows the specific bending stiffness and curvature at the end of the test of the hybrid aluminium/crossed-lamellar CFRP microstructure, along with the specific bending stiffness and the curvature at failure for selected materials from the literature. The figure shows that the bending stiffness of the microstructure is comparable to quasi-isotropic CFRPs and other aluminium/CFRP hybrid composites, but it reaches record large curvatures, exceeding the curvature at failure of any of these materials.

Figure 4: (a) An array of deflected cracks in the CFRP middle layer of a hybrid metal/crossed-lamellar composite near the end of the test; (b) the microstructure preserves its structural integrity up to record-large curvatures.

4 LARGER-SCALE HYBRID COMPOSITES

4.1 Design and prototyping

In order to establish the feasibility of replicating the previous mechanical response and preserving structural integrity, we designed (see Figure 5) and then prototyped titanium/crossed-lamellar CFRP hybrid composites with larger specimen dimensions. These microstructures were prototyped using Grade 2 titanium with a thickness of 0.05 mm.

In addition to investigating configurations a crossed-lamellar CFRP sandwiched between titanium sheets, we also studied configurations where we added 1 mm thick quasi-isotropic CFRP sub-laminates made of IM7/8552 prepreg to the hybrid microstructures in order to enhance their bending stiffness and to make them more directly relevant to engineering applications.

4.1 Mechanical testing

We tested the microstructures in four-point bending in an Instron machine. The deformation of the microstructures was monitored by capturing images of the specimens at regular intervals using a high-resolution digital camera. The displacement rate was reversed before the specimen touched the base of the test rig.

4.1 Results and discussion

Figure 6 summarises the test results of the hybrid titanium/crossed-lamellar composites. The titanium/crossed-lamellar composite could be loaded up to extremely large deformations, while retaining its structural integrity (Figure 6(a)). A detailed view of the specimen in Figure 6(b) shows that there was no discrete damage on the specimen at the maximum deflection, which suggests that the dam-

Figure 5: The hybrid metal/crossed lamellar composites were designed using a parametric unit cell FE model. The model is tessellated for visualisation purposes and shows diffuse energy dissipation in the CFRP, while the rest of the model is shown in bulk.

age in the microstructure is governed by plasticity in the titanium and in the matrix of the CFRP.

The hybrid titanium/crossed-lamellar microstructure with in-plane fibres failed progressively upon bending (Figure 6(c)). The quasi-isotropic CFRP layers were not able to accommodate the large deformations and subsequently fractured as the specimen was increasingly bent. At maximum deflection, the crossed-lamellar CFRP layer was holding the specimen together. A detailed view of the specimen in Figure 6(d) shows that, while the quasi-isotropic layers had fully lost their load carrying ca-

Figure 6: (a) The titanium/crossed-lamellar microstructure exhibited extremely large deformations under bending loads; (b) no macroscopic damage was observed in the titanium/crossed-lamellar specimen; (c) the titanium/crossed-lamellar microstructure with in-plane fibres failed progressively until the maximum displacement; (d) the crossed-lamellar CFRP layer held the hybrid specimen together without damage visible in the crossed-lamellar layer.

capacity, the crossed-lamellar CFRP layer held the specimen together and prevented it from separating into several parts. Furthermore, there was no macroscopic damage visible in the crossed-lamellar layer.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigated and proposed original high-performance carbon fibre and hybrid metal/carbon fibre composites with microstructures inspired by the natural crossed-lamellar microstructure, with the aim of enhancing the damage diffusion capability in the CFRP and hybrid composites. It can be concluded that:

- high-performance carbon-fibre and hybrid composites can replicate the damage mechanisms of the natural crossed-lamellar composite;
- CFRPs with crossed-lamellar microstructures lead to damage localisation on the tension side and damage diffusion in the middle layer;
- hybrid metal/crossed-lamellar composites preserve their structural integrity up to record large curvatures while preserving their structural integrity;
- hybrid metal/crossed-lamellar composites with in-plane fibres are resistant to separating into several parts upon bending.

In summary, this paper presented biologically-inspired crossed-lamellar microstructures for CFRP and metal/CFRP hybrid composites. These composites have interesting properties in terms of damage diffusion and they preserve their structural integrity up to extreme deformations. The new microstructures proposed here thus have potential for step changes in the design of components where structural integrity is paramount, such as containment structures.

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